

ANTI-HOAXES SOCIAL MOVEMENT OF THE INDONESIAN ANTI-DEFAMATION SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to examine the social movement conducted by MAFINDO against hoaxes in 2019. The research uses a case study design with data collected from documentation and interviews. Miles and Huberman's theory and techniques were used to analyze data through reduction, presentation, and verification. The results showed that the social movement by MAFINDO against hoaxes is voluntary. It is conducted online and offline with the spirit of cooperation, humanity, and care to change the community. The 2019 anti-hoaxes social movement was comprehensively conducted to fight hoaxes using a multipronged approach that involves 6 elements, including fact-checking, networking, advocacy, research, building/tools apps, and education. This manifested the da'wah role for Muslims and preachers towards the spread of hoaxes by information filtering. The movement is carried out with tabayyun, fostering critical thinking.

Keywords: Social movement, anti-hoaxes, and MAFINDO.

INTRODUCTION

According to Kompas and The Jakarta Post, Indonesia has the third-largest democratic system worldwide after India and the United States. However, the country is significantly affected by the spread of fake news, a disease that threatens its democratic system (Wani et al., 2021). The report from "We Are Social Hoot Suite Digital Indonesia 2019" showed that Indonesia is the fifth country to use the internet for up to 8 hours 36 minutes/day through different devices (Boididou et al., 2018).

The APJII survey (Association of Indonesian Internet Service Users) reported that internet users increased in 2017 and 2018 by 10.2% to 17.17 million people. This is around 54.68% of the country's total population of 262 million people. Based on gender, 51.43% of internet users are male, while the rest are female (Nurhayati-Wolff, 2021). Research conducted by DailySocial.id in collaboration with Jakpat Mobile Survey Platform stated that 44% of Indonesians do not detect hoaxes but have a strong desire to share unverified information immediately (Mangku et al., 2021).

According to the Ministry of Communications and Informatics, 800,000 sites in Indonesia had indications of spreading false information, including gambling and pornography. On Wednesday, 6 March 2019, the Ministry of Communications and Informatics stated that 771 hoaxes were identified from August 2018 to February 2019. There was a significant increase in the number of hoax content from January to February 2019. The AIS Team verified a total of 175 hoax contents. The number of hoaxes increased to 1,224 by March 2019 (Hidayat et al., 2021).

The Ministry of Communications and Informatics data shows that the number of hoaxes was 25 in August 2018. However, it increased to 27, 33, 53, 63, and 75 in September, October, November, and December 2018 (D. Susilo et al., 2021). There was also a dramatic increase to 175, 353, and 453 in January, February, and March 2019, respectively (Nurlatifah, 2019).

The MAFINDO R&D media release showed that the number of hoaxes was 997 in 2018. In 2019 false content was the most widely circulated type of hoaxes in the community, reaching 1221. This means there was a significant increase between these two years (Veno et al., 2021). According to the Telematics Society, 92.40% of fake news in 2017 spread through Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram, followed by the chat applications, such as WhatsApp, Line, and Telegram with 62.80% and websites 34.90% (Yasendalika et al., 2020). The MASTEL survey “2019 National Hoaxes Outbreak” stated that although there was a decrease from 2017, the spread of hoaxes was also high through social media by 87.50 %, chat applications 67.00%, websites 28.20%, and print media 6.40% (Kuntarto et al., 2021).

In 2018 the Daily Social research on 2032 internet users in Indonesia showed that 81.25%, 56.55%, 29.48%, and 39.97% of respondents received hoaxes via Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, and Telegram, respectively. Although there some hoaxes still exist on Twitter, their number is less than 30% (Flintham et al., 2018). According to the National Leadership Conference on Media Education report, literacy is involved when people accept fake news but perceive them to be true (Aufderheide, 2019). This means literacy is essential to communicate and determine the truthfulness of messages (Aufderheide & Firestone, 1993). Sharing messages without making comparisons with mainstream media may lead to conflicts (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017).

Fake news includes writings in the form of news or opinions, data, photos, and images. It is widely circulated through social networking systems, including Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, and social platforms, such as WhatsApp, Line, and BBM. Fake news is essentially a purposefully false story or account that is presented to be true. The featured stories often contain deliberately misleading information with prominent political agendas (Silverman, 2015).

According to one survey, each age category has almost the same tendency to spread hoaxes. This means that both young and old have the same level of the tendency to spread false information. Demographic and educational factors that influence a person’s tendency to spread hoaxes are the amount of spending on internet fees. The higher the level of a person internet spending, the greater the tendency to spread hoaxes (Ferdiawan et al., 2019).

The Association of Indonesian Internet Service Users shows that 88.24% of people with graduate/postgraduate education levels use the internet. This number beats the internet penetration of people with other education levels, including undergraduate at 79.23%, senior high school and equivalent 70.54%, elementary school 25.1%, and not in school 5.45%. Therefore, the internet has penetrated all community levels, including those who have not yet attended school (Zhu, 2021).

The level of higher education does not affect the ability to recognize hoaxes (Jannana et al., 2021). In May 2019, the Special Criminal Investigation Directorate of the West Java Police arrested a lecturer suspected of spreading hate speech about people power on Facebook using an account named Solatun Daulah Sayuti (SDS). The post stated that “The price of people’s lives if people power cannot be avoided is that one person shot by the police should be paid by the police being killed using a kitchen knife, machete, crowbar, car wheel wrench, and a splash of fiery paint thinner (Lynch, 2016).

This series of events shows a condition where facts and opinions are mixed, meaning that Indonesians are entering the post-truth era of the world community. The spread of hoaxes is a social phenomenon that cannot be avoided. Everyone claims to be the most correct, making facts unacceptable and distort hatred (Hatta, 2020).

Hoaxes are serious threats because their spread has metamorphosed into a business environment. Some people aim to get financial benefits through the chaos. The post-modern era of communication technology is a new subculture of users interacting virtually. Therefore, there is a need for critical literacy to receive information and avoid being trapped in the polarization of hoaxes (Kusuma, 2020).

Through the Ministry of Communications and Informatics, the government stated that law enforcement (Indonesian police) and the community need to work together to create concepts that anticipate commotion on social media to damage freedom of democratic expression. The government’s focus on “upstream” that carries out cybercrime of spreading hoaxes blocks and restricts the fight against hoaxes (Sofyani & Oktavianti, 2021). Although the fight against hoaxes is the government’s responsibility, active participation from the community is needed. This condition creates initiatives to minimize the spread of hoaxes. Therefore, there is a need for a social movement that contributes actively to overcoming hoaxes, such as the Indonesian Anti-Defamation Society (MAFINDO). This organization creates awareness regarding the dangers of hoaxes and invites the community to be educated and be literate (Sitepu et al., 2021). The social movement carried out by MAFINDO strengthens the role and position expected of a locality in the movement. According to Sidney Tarrow, the locality of a social movement develops with its own characteristics (Barkan et al., 1999).

Due to the spread of hoaxes, MAFINDO invites the entire community to be very careful with the information received. It creates awareness regarding the dangers of hoaxes to help limit their spread. The presence of this organization was also appreciated by the former Minister of Communications and Informatics, Rudiantara. According to the minister, it was originally an online organization that aims to combat false information on the internet and is now penetrating the real world. Furthermore, it has an application that helps users to verify news articles and report hoaxes (Goodwin et al., 2003).

MAFINDO cooperates with several parties, including the Google News Initiative, Training of Trainers (TOT) activities, and training activities targeting journalists, the general community, in collaboration with Internews, First Draft News, and Storyful, Siberkreasi, Indonesian Police, Health Service, IFES, and all organizations engaged in literacy education (Brown et al., 2020).

The circulation of hoaxes cannot be stopped because once the news is clarified, another hoax appears. Therefore, this research examines an organization that promotes anti-hoaxes, specifically a social movement by MAFINDO.

Problems and Goals

Based on the background described previously, the problem in this study is how to examine the social movement conducted by MAFINDO against hoaxes in 2019. Research goals is to describe anti-hoaxes social movement of the Indonesian anti-defamation society.

Research Methodology

This was qualitative research conducted through case studies (Hammersley, 1996). The data was collected using various techniques, including documentation and interviews (Busarow, 2016). The data analysis techniques used Miles and Huberman's theory, including data reduction, data presentation, and verification (Khosla, 2021).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

History of MAFINDO (Indonesian Anti-Defamation Society)

MAFINDO (Indonesian Anti-Defamation Society) is a social organization that aims to socialize the dangers of hoaxes and create immunity against hoaxes in Indonesian society. This organization started as a Facebook Forum called FAFHH (Anti-Slander, Incitement, and Hoaxes Forum). The forum was created by Harry Sufehmi in 2015 as a response to the emergence of slander, incitement, hoaxes, and hate speech on social media. Since its inception, it has pioneered anti-hoaxes, such as crowdsourced hoax busting, literacy education to the public, CekFakta.com, and public campaigns to raise awareness about hoaxes and their dangers (Kerr, 2007). Since the community members acknowledge the need for the forum, they are united in MAFINDO, chaired by Septiadji Eko Nugroho. This organization actively fights against hoaxes by conducting various activities, such as workshops and outreach on the importance of using social media to fight against hoaxes (Septiadi et al., 2020).

According to the legal document No. 1 dated 19 November 2016, the Decree of the Association Establishment Number AHU-0078919.AH.01.07, MAFINDO was established on 1 December 2016. It was officially formed by Harry Sufehmi, Judith Lubis, Catharina Widyasrini, Aribowo Sasmito, Eko Juniarto, Faisal Aditya, and Septiadji Eko Nugroho (Abdullah et al., 2019). On 8 January 2017, this organization made a breakthrough and declared the "Anti-Hoaxes Community Charter" in six cities, including Jakarta, Semarang, Surabaya, Solo, Wonosobo, and Bandung. The movement was supported by regional leaders. For instance, the Governor of Central Java took the initiative to be part of its declaration in Semarang. Ridwan Kamil also signed the Anti-Hoaxes Charter in Bandung. In Jakarta, the declaration was also attended by the former Minister of Communications and Informatics Rudiantara and the national-level officials and celebrities (Fitrya Primadhany et al., 2020).

MAFINDO has several principles: community, volunteerism, independence, neutrality, brotherhood, humanity, and universality. Regarding community as the first principle, the Turn

Back Hoaxes Movement is a community-based organization consisting of individuals who support each other to achieve the vision and goals set. In the spirit of volunteerism, MAFINDO facilitates movements based on volunteerism and discourages self-interest (Mushtaq & Benraghda, 2018).

To retain its independence, the organization has no political affiliation or dependence on any institution. Regarding neutrality, this organization is not involved in political, racial, religious, or ideological conflicts. In the principle of humanity, MAFINDO was formed based on the desire to use social media positively and resolve and minimize conflicts caused by slander, provocation, and hoaxes. Furthermore, it upholds respect for humanity, peacefully coexist, and supports the sustainability of human kind (Marques et al., 2022).

MAFINDO promotes volunteers to build understanding, friendship, cooperation, and peace with other human beings in the spirit of brotherhood. Regarding the principle of universality, this movement is present all over the world through the internet. Every volunteer has the same status and rights, and responsibilities. During the 3 years of launching, it has earned the trust of various stakeholders. As a community-based organization, the number of volunteers joining it continues to increase and spread across 18 Indonesian cities, including Ambon, Bandung, Bogor, Depok, Jakarta, Jombang, Kendari, Magelang, Makassar, Mojokerto, Pontianak, Purworejo, Semarang, Solo, Surabaya, Wonosobo, and Yogyakarta. As of 2018, this organization had been audited by an independent auditor.

Inoculation: Anti-Hoaxes Vaccine

A communication channel is a critical element in disseminating the authenticity of the information. Horlad Laswell assembled the basic components of communication in 1948. Laswell's model became a source of inspiration for the development and scientific study of subsequent communication. Since information can spread quickly through a channel, social media platforms can spread hoax messages (Herrera-Peco et al., 2021). Because social media channels often contain massive and excessive hoaxes daily, the immunity of human reason is weakened. This means it is easy to believe in fake news on their communication channels.

William J. McGuire introduced inoculation in the 1960s. It was based on the Yale group's findings of persuasion messages that present two sides of an argument in opposing beliefs (McGuire, 2013). Since the inoculation theory is a strategy to protect attitudes, changes do not occur. According to this theory, the ability to resist persuasion is determined by the individual's capability to add arguments against personal beliefs. This ability depends on two factors, including motivation and practice. The inoculation is applied within the framework of developing an anti-hoaxes strategy. This framework is currently used as the basis for formulating an anti-hoaxes strategy to eradicate hoaxes (Jumrana et al., 2019). During communication, many people are persuaded by the bigot mentality to become homo narrans. Therefore, they are easily influenced by hate viruses, ignore different arguments, do not verify the source of information, and rarely compare the information amongst themselves (Pfau & Burgoon, 1988).

The role of “vaccine” injectors is indispensable and should begin with educational institutions, mass organizations, and religious organizations. This should be followed by mass media institutions, which are expected to contribute to strengthening sound arguments against citizens. Furthermore, the way public figures behave and speak plays a critical role in the inoculation of communication (Compton & Craig, 2019). Figure 1 shows how hoaxes attack humans and the status of the fight.

Figure. 1: Hoaxes should be resisted

The anti-virus scheme on the hoax buster is the actor and the spearhead of the anti-hoax movement during the ‘anti-virus’ stage. In this case, law enforcement is the instrument. Hoax buster is an anti-virus that is expected to paralyze the virus and stop its spread (Morse, 2004). However, this requires sanctions for perpetrators to cause a deterrent effect. Electronic Information and Transaction Law (UU ITE) articles 28 paragraphs 1 and 2 and 45 can be used as a legal basis by the authorities. In the vaccine scheme, literacy is a vaccine attempted through the literacy movement. The right literacy to deal with hoaxes involves everything in terms of conception and practice.

Anti-Hoaxes Social Movement in MAFINDO

Social movements crave changes in the quality of people’s lives for the better to create joint participation in collective life. Social movements exist as a result of disappointment with the government and the ruling/authoritarian elite (Nelson & Taneja, 2018). This disappointment has become a social movement that contains people committed to change to collective life for the better without intervention from any party (Carlson, 2020). This can be seen in the movement carried out by MAFINDO to fight against massive hoaxes. The background of the existence of this organization stems from the large number of people believing in hoaxes and cannot distinguish the information mixed with opinions. The situation is increasingly troubling, with the mainstream media also spreading hoaxes.

“Our advantage is more in the long term. We educate the community about hoaxes and their dangers, and as a result, they distinguish between factual and hoax information. However, it may take longer for the results to be realized. This is because educating people cannot be as fast as blocking. In short, there is demand and supply. We provide it from the demand. when people get educated, hoaxes do not work anymore. It can be reduced but not eliminated” (Aribowo sasmito, Head of Fact Checker Committee MAFINDO) (Ilahi, 2019).

Hoaxes circulating on social media massively should awaken managers to enhance journalistic standards and place professional workers in the mass and online media as a bulwark against hoaxes. In general, mass or online media need to increase their roles and functions in truth and present empirical facts (Tarrow, 2011). The expansion of internet technology in Indonesia has facilitated a change from real living space to cyberspace. Consequently, humans communicate, express ideas and thoughts, and receive information in virtual public spaces without verifying its truth and source. Post-truth is an era where the public no longer wants to know whether the news or information received is in line with the facts or hoaxes. In this era, information or news is easily obtained and accessed via the internet (Rubin et al., 2015).

Hoax spreaders have an unmitigated threat. This is because they spread misinformation aimed at causing enmity and hatred between individuals and the community. Spreaders of fake news are threatened with imprisonment for six years and a maximum fine of 1 billion. The criminal threat is contained in Article 28 paragraph (2) in conjunction with Article 45 paragraph (2) of the Electronic Information and Transaction Law (Kang & Xiao, 2022). Hoaxes are information that contradicts existing facts but is still considered true. For this reason, they threaten the participation of citizens in the democratization process (Utami, 2018). The efforts to fight hoaxes by MAFINDO have also introduced fact-checking techniques with more innovative approaches, such as workshops, ToT, talk shows, and videos conducted in several cities and uploaded on social media.

Preventing the spread of hoaxes requires collaboration with Facebook because it is among the most popular online social networks. Based on search results, the number of users in Indonesia is at least 120 million. Fighting hoaxes voluntarily and having national and international networks have made MAFINDO social movement contribute to fighting by pursuing the literacy movement. Furthermore, online and offline activities can build a person's critical spirit in receiving and disseminating information and be more selective. Someone who produces hoaxes and distributes them has several motives, including financial and business-oriented ones.

Regarding financial motive, buzzers play critical roles in producing hoax messages. They are used by parties who deliberately invite them to play their role through high fees. An example is Saracen, a group of people who intentionally circulate hoax content related to SARA (ethnic, religious, racial, and intergroup) issues. In this regard, the hoaxes are circulated based on orders through social media. The financial benefits are obtained from the customer and Google. When hoax content producers circulate it on social media or related portals and get likes and shares from netizens, they receive financial benefits from Google AdSense (Monti, 2022). This is obtained when content receives the attention of media users in the form of viewers.

Regarding political motive, politics is always related to strength and power. During the election period, hoaxes about politics dominate more than other content. In most cases, this type of hoax is deliberately produced by groups or individuals through vilifying opponents in elections. It is carried out by successful teams or their sympathizers. Hoaxes spread by influencers, politicians, and party public figures also affect the community. They make the community becomes polarized in social and political terms.

Hoaxes with ideological motives often relate to religious issues. They become sensitive to build a discourse in virtual space through issues used to oppose the ideas of community groups. Different perspectives, such as religion and politics, promote someone to spread hoax content, polarizing the community in hatred motive. For example, the 2019 Indonesian presidential election gave rise to the terms *cebong* and *kampret*, leading to hatred in different aspects. For instance, the supporters may attack each other in cyberspace, where the information used for attacks is not necessarily a hoax.

Regarding social motive, a person rich in information spread the news even without knowing its authenticity. In case there is information that looks good and useful, it is immediately spread to others without thinking. In fun and fad motives, the posted content receives the response in the form of positive comments, likes, and others from netizens, making the hoax producers happy. The netizen's actions have opened a gap for hoax producers who deliberately create economic and political interests (Susilo et al., 2020).

Social media has political and economic powers, where those behind the spread of hoaxes control the value of the money to be created, distributed, and consumed. Political power is involved in collective decisions that determine aspects of people's lives in a particular community and social system. In case political power on social media is symmetrically distributed, a particular class or group has the power to decide. However, in case the power in social media is symmetrically distributed, every user or everyone on social media has the opportunity to be involved in decision-making. This means that hoaxes are created, produced, distributed, and consumed (Chen et al., 2014).

Hoax messages are produced and spread because of the desire to obtain profit by irresponsible actors. Fighting hoaxes circulating in the media requires a battlefield against communication messages through inoculation, a theory that offers people ways to resist persuasion messages. This is intended to make them resistant to persuasive arguments that others make (Jumrana et al., 2020).

Fighting hoaxes requires inoculation through an anti-virus that fights them and vaccines or immunity to offer protection (Budiana & Warta, 2019). According to the inoculation theory, the receiver of the message becomes resistant to attitude attacks, similar to when the body is immunized against a viral attack. A weak dose of the virus will activate the immune system. Similarly, challenges to attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors make them more resistant to change in case exposure to estimates is given in weak and small forms.

Humans need injections of vaccines and anti-virus to cope with attacks. An anti-virus weakens or kills viruses to prevent the spread of the impact directly. Similarly, vaccines help the body to develop the immune system and overcome further viral attacks, in this case, hoaxes. The movement against hoaxes by MAFINDO exists because of responding to the gap in knowledge technology that causes various problems since the information spread freely and freely. Resolving issues related to hoaxes might involve a multi-stakeholder collaborative movement with the same vision and mission and takes part in the movement against hoaxes at the national level.

The social movement conducted by MAFINDO in 2019 to fight hoaxes uses a multipronged approach. This movement involves multi-stakeholders and multi-disciplines, such as fact-checking, networking, advocacy, education, building tools/apps, and research. Figure 2 the scheme of the anti-hoaxes social movement conducted by MAFINDO.

Figure. 2: MAFINDO’s Social Movement Scheme

In terms of Fact-Checking, MAFINDO conducts daily fact checks on its channels. Fact Checks carried out by the MAFINDO on the turnbackhoax.id website archives the results of the Anti-Slander, Incitement, and Hoax (FAFHH) group discussion. Fact-checking is also applied in many countries, either as an institution or a database, regarding uncovering hoaxes. The United States has actively conducts fact-checking to expose viral hoaxes on social media using crowdsourcing mechanisms (La Porta & Zapperi, 2020).

In carrying out Fact-Checking, a crowdsourcing system is also used. “Crowdsourcing is the act of taking a function once performed by employees and outsource it to an undefined (and generally large) network of people.” (Jeff Howe, 2006)

MAFINDO openly invites the community to participate in cyberspace that relates to fact-checking. This can be carried out anytime and anywhere provided there is an internet network. Since efforts are needed to clarify hoaxes, fact-checking is important. There are three purposes of fact-checking. First, it is meant to increase understanding of the problem by responding to misinformation for the general community. Second, it aims to help multiply the culture from ‘opinion’ to a bigger fact-checking for journalists. Third, it is meant for politicians to hold news network political pundits (recently) accountable and prevent false statements.

In the networking movement, MAFINDO has a network with all elements that have a concern for hoaxes. To optimize the dissemination of information to prevent hoaxes, the organization

has a hoax content complaint service (Salgado, 2018). This is carried out to minimize the spread of hoax content on social media. There is also a TurnBackHoax.id service that invites the community to fight hoaxes together. Furthermore, the community may also report hoaxes at Kalimasada number, specifically 085921600500. Kalimasada is a collaboration between MAFINDO and WhatsApp to fight hoaxes (Kiki Anna, 2017). This is carried out because the information is easily shared in the WA chat application that ranked third with a high spread of hoaxes.

Figure 3: Hoax content complaint service

The portal is in line with the Minister of Communications and Informatics Regulation No. 19 of 2014 on Handling Internet Sites with Negative Content. This regulation contains basic rules regarding procedures for blocking internet sites with negative content that involves the role of the community and internet service providers (Astara, 2021).

MAFINDO volunteers carry out advocacy activities as a tangible manifestation of their contribution. They hold anti-hoaxes campaign activities with relatively large mass targets, conduct public advocacy against the government, and hold fundraising. Furthermore, the organization provides education with broad audience segmentation to reach all circles, including students and mothers, regardless of social strata. In 2019, it conducted education using volunteers as resource persons. There was an achievement of 18,311 audiences in one year. Anti-hoaxes education is conducted through offline socialization, CFD activities, seminars, and workshops, among others.

Thinking maturity remains the main measure of the success of an educational process that involves solving hoax-related problems. According to Catts and Lau, evaluated information leads to better literacy (Piloiu, 2016). Therefore, people need to obtain and evaluate the quality of information. With education, a person might gain access and the ability to search for information and find messages contained in a media. Analysis refers to the process of knowing the purpose of the media message creator, the intended audience, how the construction technique (message) is used, and the symbol system and technology used to construct the message.

In terms of research, the organization participates in developing science and technology, such as collaborating with PUSAD Paramadina regarding hoaxes, incitement, and hatred. Furthermore, it develops technology that the community can use to clarify news. It also has data that serves as a reference for national media to the point of being quoted by international media. This is in line with Founder and Chairman Septiadji Eko Nugroho, who stated that “Many media use MAFINDO as a reference for hoaxes. Furthermore, this organization has a research field that aims to provide findings of hoaxes” (Personal interview with Chairman and Founder of MAFINDO Septiadji Eko Nugroho).

Research helps in finding scientific innovations to test the truth and provide solutions to problems. It is an important step in developing science and technology and can strengthen or criticize previous findings. Moreover, the development carried out by MAFINDO produces tools to build an application. Supported by an IT-savvy team, it helps build technological literacy as a digital-based tool to check facts easily. Furthermore, it also makes several tools to detect hoaxes, such as WhatsApp Hoax Buster, Hoax Buster Tools/HBT, and Yudistira. Juditha stated that technology with checker application is used to check the truthfulness of information indicated as hoaxes (Aufderheide & Jaszi, 2018).

The social movement against hoaxes conducted by MAFINDO conducted a social movement that involved various stakeholders and the community through a digital security system. The community is still working together and worrying about hoaxes that can cause division. The strong inoculation of the individual makes it resistant to hoaxes. This limits the spread of hoaxes because individuals have a critical literacy level.

Social movements against hoaxes are part of da’wah activities for a Muslim. In this case, da’wah is carried out online and offline. Someone may conduct both once, including conveying messages of peace, spreading positive content, and countering hoaxes circulating through their social media accounts. Therefore, preachers need to understand digital ethics in spreading kindness through online media. The digital ethics of a preacher in carrying out da’wah using online media are as follows:

First, the message is conveyed based on the Qur’an by including the letter, verse, and hadith. Furthermore, it is conveyed straightforwardly without mixing with opinions. The material presented correlates with the phenomenon targeted by da’wah.

Second, encouragement is carried out by giving motivation. This means that the target of da’wah is encouraged through persuasion in the form of motivation without psychological pressure (Russo et al., 2021). There are four internet ethics, and preachers can adopt these in carrying out da’wah through the principle of goodness.

First, this media is very heterogeneous, meaning there is an opportunity for conflict. Second, communication in the online space often leads to misinterpretation. Third, the content is direct or indirect, hence can be addressed to anyone. Fourth, virtual user relations are transformations in the real world through technology (Neden, 2022).

Preacher activities while participating in the movement against hoaxes are Islamic value agents in today's global challenges. Therefore, preachers are expected to master technology to package the values of da'wah to the relevance of contemporary phenomena based on Qur'an and hadith, both online and offline. Fighting hoaxes is a positive activity and the teachings of goodness, as da'wah commands in surah An Nahl verse 125.

Da'wah becomes a social movement by filtering against the massive spread of hoaxes (Ahyar & Huda, 2021). The ability of the preacher to counter hoaxes is largely determined by the capability to master digital and interesting and targeted content. The nature of da'wah invites people to the truth, not lies. It is a challenge for preachers to make the community aware of the information received and invites tabayyun activities as the Qur'an provides guidelines.

CONCLUSION

This research aimed to identify and describe the anti-hoaxes social movement carried out by MAFINDO in 2019. This social movement is based on a sense of concern for hoaxes circulating on social media, especially among Indonesians who cannot clarify news. It was based on volunteerism with the spirit of cooperation as a form of love for the homeland. Due to the human value and disappointment caused by hoaxes, this organization carries out "anti-hoaxes" activities. In general, upstream and downstream social movements against hoaxes are conducted online and offline. Networking with various organizations and institutions with the same vision increases the organization's internal resources to make each activity effective in detecting hoaxes. MAFINDO used various approaches to achieve its objectives. For instance, it used a comprehensive and multipronged approach that involves six elements, including fact-checking, networking, advocacy, research, building/tools apps, and education. These elements are expected to increase community resistance to hoaxes because they have inoculation. Strong inoculation makes an individual resistant to hoaxes because of a high level of immunity, such as literacy. The anti-hoaxes social movement by MAFINDO helps improve the fact-checking ecosystem and efforts to increase digital literacy to fight hoaxes. The social movement against hoaxes is a manifestation of da'wah for preachers and Muslims. The nature of da'wah invites people to the truth, not lies. It might be challenging for preachers to make people aware of the information received and invite them to tabayyun activities as the Qur'an provides guidelines.

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